

Educational Problems of Seasonal Agricultural Worker Students in Primary Education

Hasan ASLANCAN

Cagrikanli Primary School

Yuregir/ ADANA

To cite this article: Hasan ASLANCAN, Current Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 520 – 537. - 0099-0001-2208-0414. Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

""• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic"" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

""The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

• The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

""• Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days."" ("CURRENT SCIENCE") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

Seasonal agricultural labor migration refers to the process of migrating from the place where a person or family often lives to find a job in agricultural production activities and living near the areas where agricultural production is made, mostly in tents. In Turkey, a considerable number of children take part in seasonal agricultural labor migration with their families. Most of the children who migrate with their families and even must work in fields or gardens cannot go to school in the regions they come from. Although some children can go to school, it is difficult for these children to get used to a new school environment, new teachers and friends, and to be successful in these conditions, as their education is interrupted.

Many seasonal agricultural worker families live in Adana, and in places where these families live intensively, children's education is disrupted because they cannot go to school to financially support the family during seasonal work. 15 students have joined. Data collection go-between aspect researcher by prepared meeting form has been used. The collected data were analyzed with Nvivo software.

Keywords: *Working Children, Success in Education. Seasonal Agricultural Work, Students*

1. Introduction

Every year, thousands of families in Turkey hit the road in March-April to work in seasonal jobs (especially in the agricultural sector). Most of the families who hit the road to work in seasonal agricultural works consist of landless families living in rural areas in the East and Southeast or disadvantaged family members with low socio-economic level living in the suburbs of the city centres. The adventure of seasonal agricultural worker families, who hit the road in March, continues until November. Since Turkey is an agricultural country, and its agricultural diversity is high, it also diversifies the work done. The change of season and product brings with it the change of time and place. More than three million people, struggling to survive by working in seasonal agricultural jobs, are migrating from city to city and this forced migration movement becomes routine. Families who cannot earn enough income on their own agricultural lands, who have little or no land, and unemployed and poor families in the slums and remote areas of cities, go to regions where agricultural activities are more intense and job opportunities are more in order to earn their living, and look for a job as a seasonal laborer and find jobs in the jobs they find. works (Yıldırak et al., 2003). 2

Families engaged in seasonal agricultural work in Turkey migrate as agricultural workers from Eastern and Southeastern Anatolian Regions, where families with low income, low socioeconomic status, low income and many children are common, to regions and regions where agricultural activities are intense such as the Mediterranean, Aegean, Central Anatolia and Black Sea Regions. they are doing. Seasonal

CURRENT SCIENCE

agricultural workers mostly travel with all their family members and stay at their address for only a few months of the year. Thousands of primary school-age children who go to seasonal agricultural work with their families can return to the places they went to as seasonal agricultural workers before the end of the academic year, but only after the beginning of the next academic year, that is, a few months after the schools open. Due to this seasonal agricultural migration, which does not coincide with the academic calendar of the academic year, it is clearly seen that the education of children is interrupted to a great extent, and it causes injuries that are not possible to be compensated. Although legal arrangements have been made in this area, it is obvious that there is not enough cure for this wound. Although primary school children try to continue their education in the places they go, this does not continue in a healthy way. How children who are deprived of basic education are affected by the unfavorable and difficult living conditions of seasonal agricultural workers; during the migration, which lasts about 8 months of the year, in tents with their families; It reveals that they cannot adequately reach services that are basic human rights such as health, education and social services (Akbiyık, 2008; 2011).

At the beginning of the problems experienced by the students is the problem of adaptation as they start school in the middle of the academic year. These children at the age of compulsory education become sluggish and tired due to unfavorable living conditions, and they have problems focusing on the lessons they attend (Benek & Ökten, 2011).

2. In The World Seasonal Agricultural Labor

In the world total of the workforce approximately 27% of Agriculture in the field is working (ILO, 2018). Of the approximately 1.1 billion employees working in the agricultural sector, close to 450 million from the country another to the country and country in different regions between Location is changing (Hurst, 2007). So, in the world agricultural workforce 40% of migrant workers.

Developed in countries agricultural in production great employment a partial seasonal Agriculture made up of workers. EU member states such as Spain, France and Italy It is estimated that the number of temporary workers in agriculture is higher than permanent workers. is being done. In Europe, 4,5,500,000 of them are workers from outside Europe. It is said that there are millions of agricultural workers. In the US, the agriculture sector More than 50% of the more than 2.5 million workers working are immigrants from other countries. are reported to be workers (Donham and Thelin, 2006; Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung, 2012; ILO, 2004).

In the world where children of seasonal workers have problems with education and training It is

CURRENT SCIENCE

an undeniable fact in our country as well as in our country. Problems in solving problems live of persons your thoughts and to the solution related your ideas receiving your problem solution in phase in the implementation is important.

In this context, the main purpose of the research is to decide the experiences of children of seasonal agricultural workers. is problem and solution your suggestions stakeholders by How that you are perceived determination has been decided. To achieve this goal, the following research questions was created.

- 1) students' problem and to the solution related his thoughts What are they?
- 2) of parent's problem and to the solution related his thoughts What are they?
- 3) your teacher's problem and to the solution related aspect his thoughts What are they?

3. Method

Research model

Research qualitative in approach sample event (situation work) aspect patterned. Study problems and solution proposals experienced by the children of seasonal agricultural worker families. student view in angle to be given has. Lightning and to Şimşek (2011:77) by case study an individual, an institution, a group, an environment to be studied to situations sample it could be. According to Büyüköztürk et al. (2013:21), a case study in examining a social group available. In this study, since the educational problems of the children of MTİ families are examined, because case study can be accepted as

4. Data Collection tool

An open-ended interview form was prepared as a data collection tool. expressed in the literature and study as a result curiosity made from the questions a matter pool was created. This The items were evaluated by evaluating the relevance of the subject and the response status of the target audience. open-ended question forms were created.

Study group

Study of the group in deciding maximum diversity will supply and different teaching levels also representation will be able to number of people has been selected. Study group Dense aspect in Yüreğir district of Adana province, which is one of the settlements where seasonal

CURRENT SCIENCE

workers are found. schools were selected. In these schools, seasonal workers, by the purpose of the research, parents and students has been selected. purposeful sample in the framework of maximum variation students were selected. The characteristics of the students in the study group are given in Table.at 1 presented.

Table one. students Demographic to variables Related Informations

Student	Gender	experienced Centre	studied City	School Type	Brother Number
Student A	Girl	Bay	Adana	Primary school	8
Student B	Girl	District	Adana	Middle School	6
Student C	Girl	Bay	Adana	Middle School	12
Student D	Girl	Bay	Adana	Middle School	11th
Student TO	Male	Bay	Adana	Middle School	5
Student F	Girl	Bay	Adana	Primary school	4
Student G	Male	District	Adana	Primary school	7
Student H	Girl	District	Adana	High school	8
Student I	Male	District	Adana	High school	7
Student J	Girl	Bay	Adana	Middle School	10
Student K	Girl	Bay	Adana	High school	6

CURRENT SCIENCE

Student L	Male	district	Adana	High school	9
Student M	Girl	District	Adana	Primary school	7
Student N	Male	District	Adana	Primary school	12
Student HE	Girl	Bay	Adana	Primary school	8

According to Table.1, while 10 female students took part in the study, 5 male students participated. This 8 of the students reside in the village and 7 of them reside in the district center. 6 While the student is studying in primary school, 5 students continue their education in secondary school and 4 students continue their education in high school.15 families move to Adana to work. It goes seasonally. The minimum number of siblings is 4, while the maximum is 12. average siblingnumber is 8.

Data Collection Process

The students selected for the study group were given by the researcher at the school. has been applied. Each school for separate aspect clears a day adjusted and students form your questions by reading and he doesn't understand a point by asking if they were asked to write.

Data analysis

In the analysis of the data, first, student opinions were transferred to the NVivo program, and each opinion was independent coding with coded. Crude coding a moon Then again review passed and again coded. Each two in coding similar and Differences by deciding coding reliability calculated. The similarity rate was calculated as 90%.

Table2. Student to your opinions Related Theme and of categories Definitions

Theme and Category	Definition	Sample expressions
--------------------	------------	--------------------

CURRENT SCIENCE

FAMILY	Family in the category this if related your familycodes showing support is the total	“My parents read and write. he does not know. Support they can't"
GOING LOCATION	their situation at the place of work-related codes	“Not to school, but to readingI continue”
SCHOOL	Problem solution for at school being done the one which...student views on the process. has.	
<i>affective dimension</i>	Students' affective attitudes towards school to their situation related opinions has.	"A lot I like"
<i>Added program</i>	Students' adaptations and deficiencies completion for added to work relatedideas has.	“Teacher topics cannot grow. For this with me to take care opportunity none"
SOLUTION	to the problem related students by presentedSolution proposals and requests	
<i>Education</i>	Education through problem Solution proposals	"Summer to your courses I dont go necessary"
<i>Business opportunity</i>	Solution proposal aspect work opportunity providingit is recommended	“Our family has a job opportunity here. provision.”
<i>Material supports</i>	Solution proposal aspect material supportsupplying recommended.	“Government support to familiesshould provide”
<i>not moving</i>	Solution proposal aspect of his family not to movethey want	“My family is working far away. don't go."

CURRENT SCIENCE

When Table 2. is examined, the themes of family, destination, school and solution from the students' views was created. Affective dimension and added program categories appeared in the school theme. In the solution category, education, job opportunities, financial support and not moving categories appeared. out.

5. Validity and Reliability

To ensure the internal validity of the study, various methods of data were used. To ensure this Students from different schools and different school levels were reached. Interview questions Expert review criteria were used in its preparation. To ensure transferability, purpose sampling of technique criterion sampling Type using participants attention has been paid to its determination. (Lightning and Simsek, 2011). In addition, the data collection and analysis process described in detail. (Shenton, 2004). To ensure the internal reliability of the research analysis as a result created codes clear a from the range Then coded. Similarity rate 90% aspect calculated. in hand made themes your expert crude data on you to your opinions in consultation consistency review has been made. (Miles and huberman, 1994).

6. Results

Students' opinions family (15) visited Location (30), school (46) and solution (20) be about to total(65) four themes under has been collected. Most more code to school related while producing most little code familyin the theme produced.

Table 3. students Family to the theme Related His thoughts

	Primary school		Middle School		High school		Total (15)
	Girl (2)	Male (3)	Girl (4)	Male (one)	Girl (3)	Male (2)	

CURRENT SCIENCE

Family support none	2	one	0	one	one	0	5
Family support control	0	0	0	0	0	one	one
Family support material	0	one	4	0	0	one	6
Family support moral	0	0	0	0	one	0	one
Family support	0	one	0	0	one	0	2
Total	2	3	4	one	3	2	15

When Table 3 is examined, all the female students at primary school (2) not support expression they have done. This on the subject Student HE “ *my mother my father read writing does not know* ”. One in three male students in primary school lacks family support. when specifying someone material support, they are said, other someone if of his family himself said its support. Stating that he received financial support, Student G said, “*I went to school with me. they come and go. While using the expression “ They give pocket money ”*”, Student N says “ *My mother is at home sometimes is reading a book. My father is working* ” and said that his family is supportive. to middle school continue 4 female students stated that their families supported them financially. In this regard, Student B used the expression “ *Yes, they are providing resources* ”. attend school The male student said, “ *My parents are illiterate. They cannot support* ” he said that he did not receive support. One out of three high school female students have support from her family. while another student said that he received moral support, the last student was from his family support you received expression has done. Student F “ *Yes data spiritual on the subject support gives* ” expression with spiritual support you received expression has done. to high school continue the one who male one of the students while the other student said that his family was controlling him, support you received expression has done. Student L “ *Yes. They are giving written push-up results follow-up they do* ” expression with her family checking stated.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Table 4. students Solution to your suggestions Related Feedback

	Primary school		Middle School		High school		Total(15)
	Girl (2)	Male (3)	Girl (4)	Male (one)	Girl (3)	Male (2)	
Education	one	0	5	one	0	one	8
<i>More lots your courses opening needs.</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>Education each in the field should be</i>	0	0	0	one	0	0	one
<i>Education system change</i>	0	0	0	0	0	one	one
<i>I don't go to school where we go needs.</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>Schools to our house near to be</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>to my school midway i won't let go required.</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>Summer to your courses I dont go necessary</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>Teacher more lots take care</i>	one	0	0	0	0	0	one
Business opportunity	0	0	one	0	one	0	2
<i>to our family here work opportunity provision.</i>	0	0	one	0	0	0	one
<i>Unemployment your problem unravel need</i>	0	0	0	0	one	0	one
Material supports	one	one	0	0	one	2	5

CURRENT SCIENCE

<i>Since my family is not in good condition financially support, I want.</i>	0	0	0	0	one	0	one
<i>More lots of sources to be need</i>	0	0	0	0	0	one	one
<i>State to family's money support should provide</i>	one	0	0	0	0	0	one
<i>State-supported financial difficulties We shouldn't pull.</i>	0	one	0	0	0	0	one
<i>Material support</i>	0	0	0	0	0	one	one
not moving	one	3	0	0	one	0	5
<i>My family far away to work don't go.</i>	0	one	0	0	0	0	one
<i>We from teachers let's not leave</i>	0	one	0	0	0	0	one
<i>Residence we did on the ground still We must stay.</i>	0	0	0	0	one	0	one
<i>Seasonal Location we should not change</i>							
<i>School with my family more lots let go come on</i>	0	one	0	0	0	0	one
<i>to school Search without giving continue to make</i>	one	0	0	0	0	0	one
Total	6	8	12	2	6	6	40

When Table 4 is examined, in the education category, the female student in primary school O “ *teacher is more take care* ” expression while using male students any an idea expression didn't. In the middle school part, female students used five different codes. With the expectation of more courses, they used expressions in which they said their desire to read together. For example, Student D “*We went I have to go to school in places .*” and “ *I should not leave my school unfinished.* in the form of used expressions. Student A from middle school students said, “ *Education should be in every field.* ” used an expression. While high school female students did not express an opinion on this issue, Student L , one of the students , used an expression as “ *Education system change* ”. Job opportunity in the category, a middle school female student and a high school female student expressed their opinions. Student C, one of the secondary school students , expressed as " *Providing job opportunities*

CURRENT SCIENCE

for our family here ". While using high school students, Student H said, " *Unemployment problem needs to be solved* ". used the expression. In the category of financial supports, secondary school students have an opinion on this issue. While not specifying, both female and male students from primary and high school students showed that they needed support. For example, student M " *Government financial support to families must provide* " and Student F " *My family status good is not for material support I want.* " their expressions have used. not moving in the category still middle School student's opinion they did not specify. Primary school girl from his students Student HE " *To school Search without giving continue I want to* " in the form of an expression while using male from students Student G "My family is far away. to work don't go" shaped an expression has used. to high school continue the one who girl from students Student K " *Residence we did on the ground still We must stay. Seasonal Location we should not change* " used the phrase.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Table 5. students School to the theme Related His thoughts

	Primary school		Middle School		High school		Total (15)
	Girl (2)	Male (3)	Girl (4)	Male (one)	Girl (3)	Male (2)	
Emotional dimension	4	6	8	2	5	4	29
<i>Continue don't request</i>	0	2	4	one	one	one	9
<i>Continue not to school Dislike</i>	0	one	0	0	one	one	3
<i>Don't Like School</i>	2	one	0	0	0	one	4
<i>Don't Like School</i>	2	2	4	one	3	one	13
Added program	3	3	4	2	3	2	17
<i>Separate Program there is</i>	0	one	one	0	0	0	2
<i>Separate program ineffective</i>	0	0	0	0	one	0	one
<i>Sometimes homework gives.</i>	one	0	one	0	one	0	3
<i>Teacher not interested</i>	2	2	2	one	one	2	10
<i>Class more available</i>	0	0	0	one	0	0	one
total	7	9	12	4	8	6	44

Table 5 when examined school to the theme related aspect emotional dimension to the category related Two students from primary school, five from middle school and two from high school expressed their desire to continue school. One primary school and two high school students said that they did not want to attend school. in primary school While one of the female students said that she liked the school, one student said that she did not like it. Male from students someone that you don't like when specifying the two that you love stated. Middle School girl All of the male students said that they liked the school. High school female students While all of them said that they liked the school, one of the male students said that they liked it and one of them He said that he didn't like it. In the category of added programs at school, a boy from primary school While the student said that a separate program is being made, one of the female students is that teachers sometimes do homework. they have given.

CURRENT SCIENCE

Two of the female and male students said that the teachers were not interested. they have said. Separate a program done and not done related to the question girl from students Student M “ *No, there is no program.* used the phrase ”. Middle school girls While someone said that there is a separate program, someone said that teachers sometimes give homework.and two of them said that the teacher was not interested. One of the male students in middle school “ *Usually lots more not interested. Class availability more* ” expression has used. High school girl While one of his students says that the separate program is ineffective, another student sometimes gives homework. and someone expressed an opinion on the teacher's not interested code. male students the two teachers too not interested in code thought said. All school levels When we look at the added program, when we consider that 10 student teachers are not interested, beside Only if two students separate stated that the program

7. Discussion, Conclusion and Suggestions

In this study, the educational problems of school-age children of families working as seasonal agricultural workers were examined and evaluations were made in line with the students' opinions. As a result of the study, some of the students said that they could not get support from their families about the educational problems they encountered

The point that draws attention is that most of the students who cannot receive support are female students. When the findings obtained in the studies in the field are interpreted, it is seen that there are comparable results. Considering the results obtained in the study conducted by Yiğit (2018) on seasonal agricultural workers, it is said that these workers, who are disadvantaged in terms of social rights, are also economically behind the society. It is said that the only source of income of these families is the income they earn while they work, and therefore all members of the family must work to earn more. Considering this situation, it can be thought that it is exceedingly difficult for families to supply both financial and psychological support to children.

Another result obtained in the study is that some of the participating students do not want to attend school and they also say that they do not like school. In addition, very few students said that teachers make separate programs for them. Most of the students said that the teachers did not take care of them separately. Considering another result obtained in the study, almost all of the student's state that they could not find the opportunity to attend school in the places they went.

According to the results of the analysis, it has been determined that the children of the families working as seasonal agricultural workers do not receive enough support from their families and most of the students who do not receive support are girls. In addition, it has been determined that most of the students do not like school because of school absenteeism and constant relocation. In general, students who love education believe that problems can be solved through education. Students who think that the problem will be solved with financial support said that they do not like school in general.

Since secondary school children working as seasonal agricultural workers are negatively affected by this way of working physically, socially and spiritually, this situation also negatively affects their educational life. Even if these problems cannot be eliminated, various measures can be taken to reduce them. Based on the results of our research on this subject, we can make some suggestions. Children whose parents work as seasonal agricultural workers during the school period should be provided with dormitories where they can stay until their families return, so that their education life is not interrupted. If there are Regional Boarding Schools, these children can be supported with various social and educational activities, at least at certain times of the day, under the guidance of teachers who will be assigned to these schools.

Added courses can be organized for students who start school late or leave school early due to seasonal agricultural work. Teachers and guidance counselors who supply these courses should encourage these children to be successful in their lessons and make them self-confident.

Information seminars for parents should be organized in cooperation with school administrations and guidance services about the physical and mental characteristics and needs of these children and the need for them to be successful in their education life.

Since the tents used by the families of seasonal agricultural workers as shelters or the places shown by the employer in some places are not suitable for health conditions, the state should build healthy shelters for these workers. These shelters should include bathrooms, toilets and kitchens.

8. References

- Akbiyik, n. (2008). Structure of Labor Markets in the Agricultural Sector in Turkey, *Electronic Journal of Social Sciences*. 24(7), 220-238
- Akbiyik, N. (2011). Social and Economical of Seasonal Agricultural Workers Working in Malatya

CURRENT SCIENCE

- Analysis of Problems, Electronic Journal of Social Sciences. 36(10),132-154.
- Benek, S. and Ökten, S. (2011). "A study on living conditions of the seasonal agricultural workers: hilvan county (şanlıurfa) sample." ("Mevsimlik tarım işçilerinin yaşam koşullarına ilişkin bir araştırma ...") *Gaziantep University Journal of Social Sciences Sciences* , 10 (2), 653–676. 03.09.2018 <http://dergipark.gov.tr/jss/issue/24242/257008>.
- Buyukozturk . (2013). *Scientific research methods* . Pegem, 1-360.
- Donham, K. and Thelin, A. (2006). *Agricultural medicine occupational and environmental health for the health professionals* .Blackwell Publishing. ("(PDF) Hayvancılıkta İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği")
- Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung. (2012). *Seasonal worker migration in agriculture Turkey situation summary* . Istanbul: Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung.
- Hurst, P. (2007). *Agricultural workers and their contribution to sustainable agriculture and rural development* . ("Agricultural Workers and their contribution to sustainable agriculture ...") Geneva. ILO
- ILO. (2004). *Towards a fair deal for migrant workers of the global economy* _ Genava, international Labor Office.
- ILO. (2018). Elimination Ugh worst forms Ugh child labor (WFCL) of seasonalhazelnutagriculture in Turkey. Accessed on 18 September 2018, from https://www.ilo.org/ankara/proje/cts/WCMS_373426/lang--en/index.htm
- Miles, m. B., and Huberman, a. m. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: Moment expandedsourcebook* . sage Publisher Shenton, AK(2004).Strategiesforensuringtrustwort hiness in qualitativeresearchprojects. *Educationforinformation* , 22(2), 63-75.
- Valiant, b. (2018). *Mobile seasonal Agriculture workers with local seasonal Agriculture of workers of their condition comparative analysis: Isparta province example* . Unpublished high licence thesis, Süleyman Demirel

CURRENT SCIENCE

University Social Sciences
Institute.

Yıldırak, N. (2003). *mobile and temporary in Turkeyworking and living conditions and problems of female agricultural workers* .

Agri-Business Union
Publications.

Yıldırım , A. and Şimşek , H. (2011). *Qualitative research methods in social sciences* . Ankara: SeçkinPublishing.